

Oil Revenues and Banks' Performance

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to analyze the impact of oil revenues on the performance and quality of loan portfolios of banks listed on the Saudi Capital Market (TASI) from 2013 to 2022. The study employed a panel data approach, utilizing least squares and fixed-effects regression models to analyze the data and test the study's hypotheses. The results indicated that oil revenues had no direct impact on either return on assets or return on equity. However, oil revenues had a positive impact on the share prices. In addition, oil revenues did not have direct impact, on average, on non-performing loans as a proxy for loan quality. However, negative oil prices directly declined loan quality. Moreover, oil revenues had direct and positive impacts on GDP, channeling the positive effects of oil revenues to return on assets and equity. The study contributes to the current literature by examining the effects of oil prices from various perspectives in Saudi Arabia, an oil-exporting country. It explained that the impact of oil prices on bank performance was transmitted through macroeconomic variables, such as GDP, serving as the moderating variable. Additionally, Panel Least Squares models performed better than Panel Fixed Effects models in capturing the relationship between the variables. The study's results provide valuable insights for several stakeholders, including bank management and policymakers, as they help understand how oil revenues affect bank performance using accounting-based and market-based performance indicators.

KEYWORDS: Share Price- Return on Equity- Non-Performing Loans- GDP – Panel Data

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1. Introduction

It is well known that the economic and financial performance of oil-rich exporting countries, such as Saudi Arabia, is closely tied to fluctuations in oil prices. Banks play a vital role as financial intermediaries between lenders and borrowers of money. In addition, measuring the performance of banks in oil-exporting countries, such as Saudi Arabia, is crucial for various stakeholders, including regulators, shareholders, investors, and society, as fluctuations in oil prices are among the external and exogenous factors that impact bank performance.

Study's Problem

The relationship between oil prices and bank performance varies depending on whether the country is an oil exporter or an oil importer. It also depends on the period under study and the size of the sample. Furthermore, the empirical evidence of the direction of the relationship in previous studies does not necessarily imply that this relationship will persist in the future. The relationship is influenced by factors that cause changes in prices, including demand and supply factors, as well as speculation. The relationship depends on the performance measures used. Fluctuations in oil prices affect banks through two primary factors: indirectly, via their impact on banks' risks due to macroeconomic effects, and directly, through their impact on the banks' portfolios of assets. As for the financial markets, they are directly affected by fluctuations in oil prices through the loans that banks grant to oil companies. Business cycle theory suggests that oil prices reflect global economic conditions and business innovations that stimulate crude oil markets (Yu Ma et al., 2021). Based on the mixed results in the past literature review on the impact of oil price fluctuations on banks' performance. Effendi (2019) and El-Chaarani (2019) found no impact on the bank's performance in Saudi Arabia. In contrast, El-Chagrini (2019) found a direct impact on stock prices. The mixed results may be due to methodological issues, such as the use of diverse proxies for accounting-based performance indicators and different measurements of oil revenues, as well as control variables that may overestimate or underestimate the impact of changes in oil prices on bank performance. Therefore, the current study examines the impact of oil revenues on bank performance, both directly and indirectly, from various perspectives, utilizing both least squares and fixed effects models to determine which approach is more effective in explaining the relationship.

2. Theoretical Framework

Previous studies' results differ regarding the relationship between petroleum instruments and stock market indicators. The differences are attributable to the type of data on fluctuations in oil prices. Is it symmetric or asymmetric? Furthermore, the data on stock market indicators also differs. Previous studies have employed aggregated stock market indicators, sector-level indicators, or company-level indicators (Degiannakis et al., (2018)). The target resource theory, developed by Ezzati (1976), Cremer and Isfahani (1980), and Teece (1982), is a popular theory for determining oil prices and production levels. The theory assumes that a reduction in oil production volume occurs in response to an increase in oil prices, ensuring that oil revenues meet the needs of local investments in oil-exporting countries. The target resource theory also assumes that decreasing oil prices will increase production to achieve the target revenues to finance domestic investments. Many theories explain fluctuations in oil prices, including the profit maximization theory, the demand interaction function theory, the mean return theory, and the political reversion theory. Wirl (2008). Oil price modeling is based on two theoretical approaches: the optimal control analysis approach for an exhaustible natural resource and the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries approach,

which is classified as a partial monopolist in pricing oil to maximize the net present value. However, the two methods are unsatisfactory Slaibi et al., (2009). Therefore, the authors proposed a framework for oil pricing that considers the interaction of political and military factors with the economic considerations of oil-exporting and oil-importing countries to determine a target price zone.

3. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

Sharp movements in oil prices in oil-exporting countries lead to multiple adverse effects, including increases in non-performing loans, decreases in deposits, deterioration in asset quality, and reductions in operational volume Osuma et al. (2019). Oil prices witnessed sharp fluctuations in response to geopolitical conflicts and health disasters. Oil prices experienced sharp declines from 2019 to 2021 during the coronavirus pandemic, while they witnessed noticeable increases in response to the Russian Ukrainian war that broke out in February 2022. Increasing oil prices in exporting countries enhances government spending, promotes economic stability, and improves bank profits and stock market performance. However, the decline in oil prices affects the quality of loans due to the inability to pay the principal and interest, as the private sector's contracts with the government are being renegotiated. Additionally, the decline in oil prices leads to decreases in credit ratings, increases in the cost of capital due to the risk premium, higher default rates, and an increase in non-performing loans Husain et al., (2015).

The economic growth in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia depends on oil revenues, as these affect public revenues, public expenses, and the bank's liquidity levels. Oil revenues play a crucial role in driving economic growth and enhancing financial markets. However, in non-exporting oil nations, increasing oil prices have a negative impact on the performance of banks in terms of capital adequacy, liquidity, profits, and operational efficiency. However, the adverse effects can be absorbed through economic and political stability. Morana (2017; Chi-Chana & Lee, (2019), Al-Chazal & Mirzaei (2017) noted that the increases in oil prices adversely affect the performance of banks due to the rise in defaults, corporate failures, and the increase in non-performing loans, i.e., non-accrual loans. (Poghosyan & Hesse, 2016) explained that an increase in oil prices could affect the economic growth of oil-exporting countries through both direct and indirect effects, as levels for oil-related and other activities rise, which supports bank profits and, in turn, supports the state's public finances. (Osamah et al., 2017) confirmed that fluctuations in oil prices had a significant impact on non-performing loans.

Belloum et al. (2023) examined the impact of oil price fluctuations from 1980 to 2021. The results indicated that the effects of changes in oil prices on economic growth are asymmetric, with a direct correlation between long-term increases in oil prices and economic growth. In contrast, the decrease in oil prices has no immediate impact on economic growth. Regarding inflation, there is a direct correlation between oil prices, whether rising or falling, in both the long and short term. Bugshan et al. (2023) examined the impact of oil price fluctuations on the performance of

conventional and Islamic banks in Gulf Cooperation Council countries from 2005 to 2019. Using fixed-effect regression models, the results indicated that fluctuations in oil prices had a negative and statistically significant impact on the performance of both Islamic and conventional banks. However, the effect was greater on Islamic banks. Saif-Alyousfi et al., (2020) investigated the impact of fluctuations in oil prices on the performance of banks in the Gulf Cooperation Council countries for the period 2000-2017 using the return on assets, the return on equity, and Toni's Q as proxies for banks' performance. The results indicated that oil price fluctuations directly influenced the performance of banks under study through increasing oil-related lending. However, the negative effects of fluctuations in oil prices outweighed the positive impact, and conventional banks benefited more than Islamic banks, which were more vulnerable to the negative impact of oil price fluctuations.

Esmail et al (2020) examined the impact of oil price fluctuations on the performance of conventional and Islamic banks in the Gulf Cooperation Council countries. The results indicate that oil prices, measured by the Real Price of OPEC, had a positive and statistically significant effect on ROA, ROE, and NIM, serving as proxies for profits in both the long and short terms, for both conventional and Islamic banks. Osuma et al. (2019) analyzed the impact of oil prices on the performance of 10 banks in Nigeria. The study used profits after tax, current ratio, and net interest margin as proxies for bank profits and the Average annual crude oil price as the independent variable. The study found a negative and statistically significant effect of oil prices on performance indicators during periods of declining oil prices. (Effendi, 2019) investigated the impact of oil prices on the performance of Islamic banks and the role of macroeconomic factors from 2007 to 2016. The study included 48 Islamic banks from seven countries: Saudi Arabia, Iraq, Kuwait, Bahrain, Iran, Qatar, and the United Arab Emirates (UAE). The results did not find any significant impact of oil prices on the performance of Islamic banks, likely due to their relatively low market share compared to conventional banks. The study used ROA and ROE as proxies for bank performance, and oil prices were measured as price, t-price, t-1/price, and t-1. The results for Saudi Islamic did not find direct effects of oil prices on ROA or AOE. However, oil prices had a direct impact on GDP, which in turn affected performance indicators.

El-Chaarani (2019) analyzed the impact of fluctuations in oil prices on the performance of banks, using ROA and ROE as proxies for profitability, in eight oil-producing and exporting countries in the Middle East region from 2012 to 2017. The results found direct impacts of fluctuations in oil prices on the financial performance of Bahrain, Oman, and Iran. In contrast, it did not find direct implications in Jordan, Kuwait, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and the Emirates. El-chaarani (2019) found that adverse fluctuations in oil prices had a greater impact on stock returns than the positive effects of oil prices in Bahrain and Saudi Arabia.

Ajala et al. (2021) pointed out that the impact of oil prices on stock prices was not symmetrical in the short and long term. According to the theory, AROURI et al. (2010) demonstrated that fluctuations in oil prices affect stock returns through

macroeconomic variables that influence future cash flows, particularly when the share price is a function of the discounted future cash flows. Mokni (2020) studied the impact of oil price shocks on stock returns from 1999 to 2018. The results indicated that stock returns respond more to demand shocks than to supply shocks, and demand shocks have a positive impact on stock returns in oil-exporting countries. In contrast, they have a negative impact on oil-importing countries. Kilian and Park (2009); Wang et al. (2013) noted that the reaction of stock markets to an increase in oil prices may be positive or negative. The reaction of stock markets to fluctuations in oil prices can be either positive or negative, and this depends primarily on the economy's structure in both oil-exporting and oil-importing countries. It also depends on the reasons for the increase, whether it was due to an increase in the real demand or factors related to supply.

Alharbi (2021) examined the impact of the 2015 oil price decline on the Kingdom's economic policies. The results, obtained through a questionnaire, indicated that the decline in oil prices contributed to the adoption of structural reforms in the Saudi economy and the implementation of austerity policies. Foudeh, M., (2017) found a positive relationship between increases IN oil prices and GDP in Saudi Arabia.

Lippi & Nobili (2012). Rapaport (2013) supported the argument by Kilian & Park (2009) and Wang et al. (2013), as the reaction depends on the underlying causes of the changes. The negative response of stock markets to the increase in oil prices is explained from a microeconomic perspective by the fact that companies that depend on Oil as a factor of production will have their profits and distributions affected if they do not pass on these increases to consumers Sadorsky(1999). On the other hand, from the macroeconomic perspective, increasing oil prices affect consumers through an inflation tax Basher & Sadorsky, (2006). However, in rich oil-exporting countries, the stock market responds positively to increases in oil prices due to the rise in public spending on mega projects and infrastructure investments Kilian & Park, (2009). Osama et al. (2017) examined the impact of fluctuations in oil prices on the quality of the loan portfolio. The study employed fixed-effect regression, dynamic, and GMM models for the period 2000-2014, encompassing 2,310 commercial banks operating in 30 oil-exporting countries. The results indicated that movements in oil prices have a significant impact on non-performing loans.

Alodayni (2016) confirmed that declines in oil prices as exogenous variables hurt non-performing loans. (Saif-Alyousfi et al., 2018) analyzed the impact of fluctuations in oil and gas prices on the non-performing loans of commercial and Islamic banks in Qatar from 2000 to 2016. The results indicated that fluctuations in oil and gas prices did not have a direct impact on non-performing loans. However, macroeconomic-specific factors and bank-specific variables transferred the impact of oil and gas prices to non-performing loans. Chin et al. (2023) investigated the impact of oil price fluctuations on 18 banks in Kazakhstan from 2009 to 2020, focusing on non-performing loans. The results revealed an inverse relationship, indicating that

negative oil prices hurt credit quality, and vice versa. Idris & Nayan, (2017) confirmed an inverse relationship between increases in oil prices and non-performing loans.

The study developed research hypotheses based on the literature review to reflect the direct impact of oil revenue fluctuations, without introducing additional explanatory variables at the bank or macroeconomic levels, thereby avoiding the interaction of oil prices with any control variables.

1. Oil revenues have a direct impact on Saudi banks' accounting-based performance indicators.
2. Oil revenues have a direct impact on Saudi banks' market-based performance indicators.
3. Oil revenues have a direct impact on Saudi banks' non-performing loans.
4. Oil revenues have a positive impact on Saudi Arabia's gross domestic product (GDP).
5. GDP has a direct impact on Saudi banks' accounting-based performance indicators.
6. Do fluctuations in oil prices transfer into fluctuations in stock prices?

4. Methodology and Analysis of Results

The study was conducted on all 10 banks registered on the Saudi Stock Exchange (TASI) for the period 2013-2022, collecting data on return on assets, return on equity, loans, and non-performing loans from their annual financial reports. In addition, the study obtained oil revenue and GDP data from official sources of the Ministry of Finance of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as well as share prices from the TADAWUL website. The study employed time-series cross-section panel data with fixed effects and least squares regression models to test its hypotheses.

Variables: Definition and Measurement

The study applied to Saudi banks registered on the Saudi Arabian Stock Market (TASI) and did not use additional explanatory variables, as it aimed to investigate the direct impact of oil revenues on accounting-based and market-based indicators, and the effect on loan quality, without any interactions with control variables.

Variable Code	Variable Definition and Measurement
ROA	Income after tax divided by the average assets is a proxy for the accounting-based profit indicator.
ROE	Income after tax is divided by the average equity as a proxy for accounting-based profit indicators.
SP	The share price for each bank at the end of the year is a proxy for a market-based indicator
GDP	Gross domestic product %
Oil revenues	The natural logarithm of the annual oil revenues, denominated in Saudi Arabian riyals (SAR) billion. The study used that measure as a proxy for oil prices in the fundamental analysis.

NPL	Non-performing loans at the end of the year in Saudi Arabian Riyals (SAR).
Dummy variable	The dummy variable measures the impact of a negative growth rate in oil revenues, assigning a value of 1 to years with negative growth rates and 0 to years with favorable growth rates in oil revenues.
% Oil	The study used annual increases and decreases in oil revenues as a proxy for oil prices in the robustness analysis. Oil revenues% % for the period = Oil revenues t—Oil revenues t-1/ Oil revenues t-1*100.

Source: Based On the Previous Literature

The results of the regression models show the net influence of fluctuations in oil revenues on average. Therefore, the study will not capture the impact of negative prices on the dependent variables. Therefore, the study employed a dummy variable to distinguish between the effects of years with negative and positive price rates, allowing for separate analysis. The study employed the natural logarithm of oil revenues for the primary analysis and then utilized percentage increases and decreases in oil revenues to assess robustness.

Model Specification

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{oil revenues } t + \text{Dummy } t + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{oil revenues } t + \text{Dummy } t + \mu_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$SP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{oil revenues } t + \text{Dummy } t + \mu_{it} \quad (3)$$

$$GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{oil revenues } t + \text{Dummy } t + \mu_{it} \quad (4)$$

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + GDP_t + \mu_{it} \quad (5)$$

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GDP_t + \mu_{it} \quad (6)$$

$$SP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GDP_t + \mu_{it} \quad (7)$$

$$NPL_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NPL_{it-1} + \beta_2 \text{oil } \% t + \text{Dummy } t + \mu_{it} \quad (8)$$

Where $i = 1, N$ $t = 1, T$

Analysis of Results

Table 1 presents the descriptive analysis of the study variables, where the mean of non-performing loans reached 2.3 billion Saudi riyals. In comparison, the average total loans reached 141 billion Saudi riyals, accounting for 1.6% of total loans, a ratio that is internationally accepted. On the other hand, the mean allowance for loan losses reached 3.7 billion Saudi riyals, accounting for 2.7% of total loans that covered all non-performing loans. The study period witnessed sharp fluctuations in oil revenues, recording a maximum of 913 billion Saudi riyals and a minimum of 324 billion Saudi riyals with a high standard deviation of 324 billion Saudi riyals because of the demand shock for the years 2020-2021, then an increase during the year 2022 due to the supply shock. GDP was volatile, with the minimum and maximum values recorded at -0.04 and 0.087, respectively. The standard deviation of ROE is high due to the significant differences between the maximum and minimum values.

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis

	NPL	TOTA LOANS	ALL	Oil Revenues	GDP
Mean	2334530.	1.41E+08	3370572.	598.5455	0.022492
Median	1517374.	1.21E+08	2641498.	562.0000	0.027000
Maximum	9881072.	5.76E+08	11407864	913.0000	0.087000
Minimum	302482.0	2855263.	328487.0	324.0000	-0.041400
Std. Dev.	2138342.	1.07E+08	2431543.	196.8612	0.031969
Skewness	1.842676	2.004898	1.088738	0.344471	-0.027527
Kurtosis	6.299209	7.876524	3.854195	1.727412	3.436282
	OIL%	Share price	ROA	ROE	
Mean	0.077176	25.21384	0.112572	2.383535	
Median	0.088423	21.17000	0.116536	2.050000	
Maximum	0.152262	88.64000	0.219083	6.340000	
Minimum			-		
	-0.031373	10.00000	0.082101	-2.010000	
Std. Dev.	0.059912	13.83306	0.047654	1.362446	
Skewness			-		
	-0.652156	1.824286	0.798859	0.497167	
Kurtosis	1.981315	7.738306	5.038986	3.923245	

The regression model results did not find a statistically significant impact of oil revenues on ROA, as indicated by both the least squares model and the fixed effects model, based on the probability value. Therefore, the study rejected the alternative hypothesis and accepted the null hypothesis. i.e., Oil revenues had no direct impact on the return on assets ROA. See Table 2

Table 2: Model 1

Panel Least Squares			Panel Fixed Effects Tests	
	R-Squared	0.417770	R-Squared	0.009016
	Adjusted R-Squared	0.344992	Adjusted R-Squared	-0.011630
	S.E. Of Regression	0.038997	S.E. Of Regression	1.370345
	Sum Squared Residual	0.133824	Sum Squared Residual	180.2732
	Log-Likelihood	188.9261	Log-Likelihood	-170.1429
	F-Statistic	5.740280	F-Statistic	0.436686
	Probability(F-Statistic)	0.000001	Probability(F-Statistic)	0.647451
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
Oil Revenues	1.130418	0.2614	0.567205	0.5719
Dummy	-0.436351	0.6637	-0.455239	0.6500
C	6.727408	0.0000	3.960778	0.0001

Dependent Variable ROA

The results of regression model 2 did not reveal any statistically significant impact. According to the least squares and fixed effects models, oil revenues have a significant impact on the return on equity ROE. Therefore, the study accepted the null hypothesis and rejected the alternative hypothesis. i.e., Oil revenues had no direct impact on the return on equity ROE. See table 3

Table 3: Model 2

Panel Least Squares			Panel Fixed Effects Tests	
	R-Squared	0.707415	R-Squared	0.009016
	Adjusted R-Squared	0.670421	Adjusted R-Squared	-0.011630
	S.E. Of The Regression	0.782166	S.E. Of Regression	1.370345
	Sum Of Squared Residual	53.22512	Sum Of Squared Residual	180.2732
	Log-Likelihood	-109.7557	Log-Likelihood	-170.1429
	F-Statistic	19.12267	F-Statistic	0.436686
	Probability(F-Statistic)	0.000000	Probability(F-Statistic)	0.647451
Variables	T-Statistic	Probability	T-Statistic	Probability
Oil Revenues	1.130418	0.2614	0.567205	0.5719
Dummy	-0.436351	0.6637	-0.455239	0.6500
C	6.727408	0.0000	3.960778	0.0001

Dependent Variable ROE

The results of the Panel Least Squares regression model 3 found a positive and statistically significant impact of oil revenues on the share price. In addition, the dummy variable showed an inverse and statistically significant effect on share price; that is, negative oil prices decreased the share price. However, the Panel Fixed Effects model did not find a statistically significant impact on share price. Least-squares regression models were better than fixed-effects models for capturing the impact of oil revenues on the share price. See table (4). The study accepts the alternative hypothesis, i.e., that oil revenues have a direct effect on the share price.

Table 4: Model 3

Panel Least Squares			Panel Fixed Effects Tests	
	R-squared	0.600561	R-squared	0.074825
	Adjusted R-squared	0.550631	Adjusted R-squared	0.055749
	S.E. of regression	9.285615	S.E. of regression	13.46024
	Sum of squared residual	7587.594	Sum of squared residual	17574.28
	Log-likelihood	-358.3488	Log-likelihood	-400.3449
	F-statistic	12.02809	F-statistic	3.922502
	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000	Probability(F-statistic)	0.023007
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
Oil Revenues	1.715291	0.0898	1.183302	0.2396
Dummy	-2.697760	0.0084	-1.861063	0.0658
C	6.079555	0.0000	4.194011	0.0001

Dependent Share Price

The study did not provide empirical evidence on the direct impact of oil revenues on accounting-based indicators, specifically ROA and ROE. Therefore, it examines whether oil revenues have an indirect impact on ROA and ROE in relation to GDP. To achieve this, it first examines the impact of oil revenues on GDP and then investigates the effects of GDP on ROA and ROE. The results of the least-squares regression model and the fixed-effects regression model indicate positive

and statistically significant effects of oil prices on GDP, specifically that a 1% increase in oil revenues result in a 5.7% increase in GDP, as indicated by the t-statistics. In addition, the dummy variable had an inverse and statistically significant impact on GDP, indicating that negative oil prices were associated with a decrease in GDP. Panel Fixed Effects had more explanatory power than Panel Least Squares. See Table 5. Based on the results, the study accepts the alternative hypothesis, i.e., that oil revenues have a direct and positive effect on GDP.

Table 5: Model 4

Panel Least Squares			Panel Fixed Effects	
	R-squared	0.391715	R-squared	0.391715
	Adjusted R-squared	0.315679	Adjusted R-squared	0.379173
	S.E. of regression	0.026360	S.E. of regression	0.025107
	Sum squared residual	0.061146	Sum of squared residual	0.061146
	Log likelihood	228.0894	Log likelihood	228.0894
	F-statistic	5.151730	F-statistic	31.23236
	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000003	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
Oil Revenues	5.700550	0.0000	5.984961	0.0000
Dummy	-2.252166	0.0268	-2.364530	0.0200
C	-2.022473	0.0462	-2.123378	0.0363

Dependent Variable -GDP

Table 6 showed that GDP had a positive and statistically significant impact on ROA, as indicated by the t-statistics. Additionally, the Panel Least Squares model was more effective than the Panel Fixed Effects model in terms of explanatory power, as evidenced by the Adjusted R-squared values, which were 0.882570 and 0.325300, respectively. The study accepts the alternative hypothesis, i.e., that GDP has a direct and positive effect on ROA.

Table 6: Model 5

Panel Least Squares			Panel Fixed Effects	
	R-squared	0.908050	R-squared	0.330776
	Adjusted R-squared	0.897787	Adjusted R-squared	0.330097
	S.E. of regression	0.011987	S.E. of regression	0.030688
	Sum squared residual	0.127455	Sum squared residual	0.927633
	Log-likelihood	3018.633	Log-likelihood	2039.099
	F-statistic	88.48018	F-statistic	486.8543
	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
GDP	8.080138	0.0000	22.06478	0.0000
C	27.62704	0.0000	7.525768	0.0000

Dependent- ROA

Table 7 showed that GDP had a positive and statistically significant impact on ROE, as indicated by the probability and t-statistic. The Panel Least Squares model explained 0.919830 of the changes in ROE. In contrast, the Panel Fixed Effects model explained only 0.305413 of the changes in ROE, as indicated by the Adjusted R-squared. Therefore, Panel Least Squares models were more effective than Panel Fixed Effects models in capturing the impact of GDP on ROE. The study accepts the alternative hypothesis that GDP has a direct and positive effect on ROE.

Table 7: Model 6

Panel Least Squares			Panel Fixed Effects	
	R-squared	0.927888	R-squared	0.306118
	Adjusted R-squared	0.919830	Adjusted R-squared	0.305413
	S.E. of regression	0.236617	S.E. of regression	0.696470
	Sum of squared residual	49.60488	Sum of squared residual	477.3097
	Log likelihood	74.78316	Log likelihood	-1041.406
	F-statistic	115.1554	F-statistic	434.1096
	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
GDP	9.425749	0.0000	20.83530	0.0000
C	28.92945	0.0000	6.795947	0.0000

Dependent Variable- ROE

Table 8 showed that GDP had a positive and statistically significant effect on share price, as indicated by probability and t-statistics. Both least squares and fixed-effect regression models were statistically significant. In addition, the results showed that the Panel Least Squares models were better than the Panel Fixed Effects models, as they explained by 0.882570 changes in share price compared to 0.325300 changes in the fixed effects regression model, as indicated by the Adjusted R-squared value. The study accepts the alternative hypothesis that GDP has a direct and positive impact on share Price.

Table 8: Model 7

Panel Least Squares			Panel Fixed Effects	
	R-squared	0.894360	R-squared	0.325984
	Adjusted R-squared	0.882570	Adjusted R-squared	0.325300
	S.E. of regression	3.025150	S.E. of regression	7.251233
	Sum squared residual	8117.407	Sum of squared residual	51791.68
	Log-likelihood	-2440.344	Log-likelihood	-3354.908
	F-statistic	75.85313	F-statistic	476.3900
	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
GDP	9.870091	0.0000	21.82636	0.0000
C	23.89341	0.0000	6.951569	0.0000

Dependent Variable -Share Price

The results of the least-squares regression and fixed-effects regression models did not reveal a direct and statistically significant impact of oil revenues on non-performing loans, which were used as a proxy for loan quality. The study rejected the alternative hypothesis and accepted the null hypothesis: oil revenues did not have a direct effect on non-performing loans, serving as a proxy for loan quality. However, negative oil prices as a dummy variable directly affected non-performing loans. See Table 11, Robustness Checking.

Table 9: Model 8

Panel Least Squares			Panel Fixed Effects	
	R-squared	0.849259	R-squared	0.835123
	Adjusted R-squared	0.828468	Adjusted R-squared	0.829971
	S.E. of regression	881141.9	S.E. of regression	877272.5
	Sum of squared residual	6.75E+13	Sum of squared residual	7.39E+13
	Log likelihood	-1503.828	Log-likelihood	-1508.310
	F-statistic	40.84585	F-statistic	162.0843
	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
NPL t-1	13.99884	0.0000	21.93313	0.0000
Oil Revenues	-1.338428	0.1842	-1.381361	0.1704
Dummy	-0.451570	0.6527	-0.250677	0.8026
C	2.242969	0.0274	1.721014	0.0885

Dependent Variable –NPL

Robustness Checking

To assess the robustness of the results and investigate whether the findings were sensitive to the measurement of oil revenues, the study employed oil revenues in SAR billions in its fundamental analysis. Therefore, the study used the annual percentage of increases and decreases in oil revenues. The study was rerun to compare the results. The robustness checking confirmed the basic analysis results, i.e., the study found a direct impact of oil percentage on ROA and ROE as per the probability. See Tables 10 and 11

Table 10: Model 1

Panel Least Squares			Fixed Effects Tests	
	R-squared	0.410688	R-squared	0.006024
	Adjusted R-squared	0.337024	Adjusted R-squared	-0.014470
	S.E. of regression	0.039233	S.E. of regression	0.048531
	Sum of squared residual	0.135452	Sum of squared residual	0.228463
	Log likelihood	188.3216	Log likelihood	162.1838
	F-statistic	5.575157	F-statistic	0.293956
	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000001	Probability(F-statistic)	0.745971
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
Oil %	-0.746861	0.4571	-0.603767	0.5474

Dummy	-0.398155	0.6915	-0.321870	0.7482
C	16.90043	0.0000	13.66240	0.0000

Dependent Variable –ROA

Table 11: Model 2

Panel Least Squares			Fixed Effects Tests	
	R-squared	0.709884	R-squared	0.016221
	Adjusted R-squared	0.673203	Adjusted R-squared	-0.004274
	S.E. of regression	0.778858	S.E. of regression	1.365354
	Sum of squared residual	52.77589	Sum of squared residual	178.9625
	Log-likelihood	-109.3362	Log-likelihood	-169.7817
	F-statistic	19.35276	F-statistic	0.791443
	Probability(F-statistic)		Probability(F-statistic)	0.456125
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
Oil %	-1.424523	0.1579	-1.013506	0.3134
Dummy	-0.637012	0.5258	-0.505195	0.6146
C	18.42645	0.0000	10.74809	0.0000

Dependent Variable - ROE

The Robustness checking results confirmed the basic analysis results, which showed a positive and statistically significant impact of oil revenues on share prices. Negative oil revenues resulted in decreases in share prices, as indicated by the t-statistics of the dummy. See Table 12

Table 12: Model 3

Panel Least Squares			Fixed Effects Tests	
	R-squared	0.723148	R-squared	0.197412
	Adjusted R-squared	0.688542	Adjusted R-squared	0.180864
	S.E. of regression	7.730527	S.E. of regression	12.53682
	Sum of squared residual	5258.973	Sum of squared residual	15245.66
	Log-likelihood	-340.0199	Log-likelihood	-393.2379
	F-statistic	20.89633	F-statistic	11.92951
	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000023
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
Oil %	6.573472	0.0000	4.053374	0.0001
Dummy	-5.807630	0.0000	-3.581136	0.0005
C	16.71123	0.0000	10.30458	0.0000

Dependent Variable -Share Price

The Robustness checking results confirmed the fundamental analysis, which showed a positive impact of oil revenues on GDP as a percentage of oil. In addition, negative oil rates resulted in a decrease in GDP, as indicated by the t-statistic of the dummy variable. See Table 13

Table 13: Model 4

Panel Least Squares			Panel Fixed Effects	
	R-squared	0.219091	R-squared	0.219091

	Adjusted R-squared	0.121477	Adjusted R-squared	0.202990
	S.E. of regression	0.029867	S.E. of regression	0.028447
	Sum squared residual	0.078498	Sum of squared residual	0.078498
	Log likelihood	215.5986	Log likelihood	215.5986
	F-statistic	2.244471	F-statistic	13.60710
	Probability(F-statistic)	0.018622	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000006
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
Oil %	2.420730	0.0175	2.541505	0.0126
Dummy	-4.778178	0.0000	-5.016570	0.0000
C	5.090702	0.0000	5.344686	0.0000

Dependent Variable: GDP Robustness checking- Eviews software

Robustness checking revealed that negative oil rates had a direct impact on NPL, as indicated by the t-statistic and the Probability of the dummy variable. Negative growth rates in oil revenues increased NPL, which, in other words, reduced loan quality. See Table 14

Table 14: Model 5

Panel Least Squares			Panel Fixed Effects	
	R-squared	0.850064	R-squared	0.832624
	Adjusted R-squared	0.829384	Adjusted R-squared	0.827394
	S.E. of regression	878785.5	S.E. of regression	883896.1
	Sum of squared residual	6.72E+13	Sum of squared residual	7.50E+13
	Log-likelihood	-1503.560	Log-likelihood	-1509.062
	F-statistic	41.10412	F-statistic	159.1863
	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000	Probability(F-statistic)	0.000000
Variables	t-Statistic	Probability	t-Statistic	Probability
NPL t-1	1.506056	0.1357	0.668028	0.5057
Oil %	-0.403238	0.6878	0.122675	0.9026
Dummy	11.88229	0.0000	20.41560	0.0000
C	1.855429	0.0669	0.748788	0.4558

Dependent Variable -NPL

5. Discussions

The study aimed to investigate the impacts of oil revenues on accounting-based and market-based performance indicators. Additionally, the impact on loan quality of banks registered on the Saudi Stock Market (TASI) for the period 2013-2022. The study collected secondary data from the annual financial reports, the official websites of the Saudi Arabian Stock Exchange (Tadawul), and the Kingdom's Ministry of Finance. The study employed the panel data methodology, utilizing ordinary least squares regression and fixed effects regression models to analyze the data and test the study's hypotheses. The study employed the natural logarithm of oil revenues as a proxy for oil prices in the fundamental analysis, and rates of annual increases and decreases were used in robustness checking, along with a dummy variable to capture negative oil revenues on the dependent variables. The study

used ROA and ROE as proxies for accounting-based profit indicators and share price as a proxy for market-based indicators to serve as dependent variables. The basic analysis results indicated that oil prices did not have a direct impact on ROA or ROE. The results supported the results of Effendi (2019) and El-Chairman (2019). However, the study did not support the results of Esmail et al. (2020), who found positive impacts, and Osuma et al. (2019), who found negative impacts. However, oil prices directly affected share prices, i.e., the Saudi stock market reacted positively to rising oil prices and negatively to falling oil prices, and these results supported the argument (Basher & Sadorsky, 2006; Kilian & Park, 2009). The study investigated whether oil prices indirectly affect ROA and ROE through GDP, i.e., Oil revenues affect GDP, which in turn affects ROA and ROE. The results showed that oil revenues had a positive impact on GDP, and GDP, in turn, had a positive impact on ROA and ROE. That is, oil prices indirectly and positively affect ROA and ROE through their impact on GDP. The results showed that oil revenues did not have a direct impact on non-performing loans, serving as a proxy for loan quality, on average, in the fundamental analysis. However, the robust analysis found that a dummy variable that captured negative oil revenues contributed to decreases in loan quality. The results supported those of Saif-Alyousfi et al. (2018) and contradicted those of Osamah et al. (2017), who found a direct impact. The results of the robustness check, which used annual rates of increase and decrease in oil prices as a proxy for oil prices, confirmed the basic analysis results. However, it provided empirical evidence that negative oil revenues have a direct impact on loan quality. Negative oil prices decrease loan quality or increase non-performing loans. The results supported those of Chin et al. (2023) and IDRIS & NAYAN (2017).

6. Study's Contributions

The current study stands out from previous studies in its multifaceted nature, examining the direct and indirect effects of fluctuations in oil revenues on traditional accounting performance indicators and loan quality, as well as their impact on bank stock prices. In addition, the study employed least squares regression models with fixed effects to assess the sensitivity of the results to the regression model used, as the results indicated that the least squares regression model performs better than the fixed effects regression models in explaining the relationship between the variables. Therefore, the study's results will have significant implications for policymakers, investors, and banks.

7. Study's Limitations and Recommendations

The study employed the case study method, which enables an in-depth examination of the phenomenon under investigation. However, the results of the case study cannot be generalized to other countries or at a different time. Therefore, the study recommends expanding the scope of the current research by conducting a cross-country study of oil-exporting countries to derive new theories explaining the complex nexus between fluctuations in oil prices and micro and macro variables.

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